

AN EXTENDED THICKNESS-DEPENDENT MOISTURE ABSORPTION MODEL FOR UNIDIRECTIONAL CARBON/EPOXY COMPOSITES

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Introduction

- Composite materials used in outdoor applications are inevitably subjected to environmental attack, which may lead to premature failure of the structures.
- Accelerated tests are usually conducted in laboratory. However, sometimes the amount of time needed to reach saturation is still relatively long, especially when **non-Fickian** behaviour is observed.
- Hence, there is a need to investigate the relationship between the moisture absorption behaviour and the **thickness** of the materials.

Materials and Methods

- Material: **AS4/8552 carbon/epoxy composite**
 - Density of AS4 carbon fibre: 1.79 g/cm³
 - Density of 8552 epoxy resin: 1.30 g/cm³
 - Fibre volume fraction: 57.42%
 - Ply thickness: 0.13mm
- Stacking sequence: **unidirectional**
- Fabrication: **autoclave** at Composites Technology Research Malaysia (CTRM)
- Number of plies: **4, 8 and 16**
- Specimens size: **5×5 cm²** with sealed edge
- Water absorption test: **60°C** in **distilled water**

Thickness-dependent Moisture Absorption Model

$$M(t) = M_I(t) + M_{II}(t)$$

$$= \phi M_m \{1 - \exp[-7.3(D_z \cdot t/h^2)^{0.75}]\} + (1-\phi)M_m \{1 - \exp[-(\alpha < t-t_o >)^{0.75}]\}$$

Moisture Absorption Curves

No. ply	M_m (%)	ϕ	α (day ⁻¹)	t_o (day)
4	1.10	0.2923	0.0194	1.0
8	1.41	0.2286	0.0201	3.0
16	2.33	0.1378	0.0042	11.2

Generalised non-Fickian Parameters

